

At a Glance

Acronym: HumAlne

Title: Hybrid Human-AI Decision Support for Enhanced Human Empowerment in Dynamic Situations

Call identifier: HORIZON-CL4-2022-HUMAN-02

Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2022-HUMAN-02-01

Total Budget: € 7,658,375

Project duration: 36 months

Start Date: 1st October 2023

HumAlne is a joint effort of **17 partners** to create a revolutionary **Operating System platform** for enhancing the **collaboration between Humans and AI** across various industrial sectors.

This platform integrates **advanced AI learning paradigms**, such as Active Learning, Neuro Symbolic Learning, Swarm Learning, and eXplainable AI, in dynamic, unstructured environments across **5 sectors**, acting as project pilots.

Contact us

For more information on the HumAlne project please contact us at: info@humaine-horizon.eu

Project Coordinator: GFT ITALIA SRL

Consortium

The **HumAlne consortium** is formed by **17 partners** from 12 countries which namely are **Italy, Israel, Greece, Slovenia, Germany, Netherlands, Bulgaria, Spain, Belgium, Cyprus, Portugal, United Kingdom.**

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Hybrid Human-AI Decision Support for Enhanced Human Empowerment in Dynamic Situations

Making the best out of Humans & Artificial Intelligence Systems Collaboration

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The challenge

Can **humans** and **Artificial Intelligence (AI)** effectively **collaborate** in dynamic, unstructured environments? What if AI systems went **beyond automating simple tasks** and could support entire workflows where **humans interact with AI systems**?

In a world where AI plays a vital role in decision-making, **the need for AI systems** that enhance the unique **flexibility** and **intelligence of humans is more important than ever**.

What is HumAlne?

The EU-funded **HumAlne** project is developing an innovative **Operating System (OS)** designed to foster **collaboration between humans and AI**. Our goal is to empower the creation of **advanced decision-making** applications across **various industries**. By combining human input with AI, HumAlne aims to build **systems that exceed the capabilities of AI and humans working independently**.

The **HumAlne OS platform** is designed to manage both structured and unstructured data, **integrating human inputs through advanced technologies** like ontologies, knowledge graphs, and semantic interoperability.

Additionally, HumAlne is creating **resources** such as **training** and nurturing a **vibrant community** to drive the adoption and impact of the project's outcomes.

The HumAlne Technologies & Pilots

The HumAlne project invests in **advanced AI learning paradigms**, such as

- Active Learning,
- Neuro Symbolic Learning,
- Swarm Learning,
- eXplainable AI

which are all used in the HumAlne OS Platform.

These cutting-edge AI paradigms place **the human operator at the centre**, offering complete control and understanding of the operations performed, and ensuring **seamless collaboration between humans and AI**.

The HumAlne technologies are applied to **5 “Smart” Pilots** that span diverse industries with different needs. In each of these areas, the **combination of Human expertise and AI applications is what makes them “Smart.”**

Smart Manufacturing

Smart Cities

Smart Healthcare

Smart Finance

Smart Energy

Who benefits from HumAlne?

European AI researchers gain access to advanced frameworks, models, algorithms, benchmarks, datasets, and training to drive human-centered AI innovation.

Vendors and AI Solution Providers leverage HumAlne OS to reduce development costs and accelerate human-centric AI solutions.

End-Users, Workers, Citizens enhance work performance with inclusive, trusted AI solutions focused on human values.

Expected Impact of HumAlne

Boost **human-AI collaboration** for advanced decision-making.

Increased **AI transparency** and fairness.

Significant **advancements** in the **European research ecosystem**.

Economic growth through trusted, high-performing human-centric applications.